

CHARACTERISTICS OF THE CLUSTER APPROACH OF TEACHING ENGLISH TO PUPILS IN SCHOOLS

Sobirova Dilorom Haydaraliyevna

teacher of GulSU, Uzbekistan

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Abstract. *The purpose of this article is to establish the effectiveness of cluster systems as a strategy to enhance the teaching and learning of foreign languages in the educational system. It is devoted to the idea of a pedagogical educational cluster, describing its necessity, implementation procedures, principles, and directions.*

Keywords: *foreign languages, method, training, knowledge, clustering process.*

The information and abilities outlined in these state educational standards are what teachers aim to impart to their students. Only when a student accepts and comprehends the material or when they can demonstrate in practice the tasks intended to develop their skills can teaching be deemed successful.

One of the most crucial aspects of communication is language, which is also a tool for international communication. English is a crucial international language that has many connections to the many facets of human existence. English is becoming more vital in every aspect of life today. Because of this, English must be taught in every level of education, including universities.

In addition, science, art, and advanced technology are all conducted in English. Since many books are written in English, anyone who wish to learn about science and advanced technologies should be fluent in the language.

The four abilities listed below are essential for English learners to master. They are speaking, reading, writing, and listening. The study of some language features, such as structure, vocabulary, and pronunciation, is necessary for developing these abilities since they will aid in the development of clearer, more effective communication.

As is common knowledge, there are three different approaches to teaching foreign languages. They include interactive methods, active methods, and passive approaches. It should be highlighted that a teacher is at the heart of instruction in passive approaches. He takes an active role, while the students do not. Questions, individual and group work, assessments, and other forms of control can all be used. When used by an experienced teacher, it might be helpful. Second, learners participate actively in active techniques. Their participation and role in the engagement process are both equal. Students are free to ask questions and discuss ideas with a teacher. A modernized version of active methods, the last but now first interactive method or approach. Most educators often mean or understand cooperative learning during the class. But in this case, inner action should also be given emphasis. The students should be internally motivated to work hard or actively participate in the class. In the interactive approach, the teacher's job is to guide the students' actions toward achieving the lesson's objectives, which may involve interactive activities and tasks.

The clustering technique is one of many that can be applied to the teaching or learning of foreign languages. It is currently one of the most popular approaches for teaching foreign languages. It can be applied at all levels of English instruction for both young and older students.

It is the method through which the words are actually delivered that are closely related to the "topic/theme" offered. This method will aid in the students' vocabulary growth. Additionally, the clustering method might stimulate their minds. This method works well for building their concepts. Utilizing the clustering technique will also make it simpler for pupils to understand the target word's meaning, memorize it, and apply it when they recognize the appropriate circumstance based on previously understood context cues. Additionally, it is entertaining so that the kids would find language learning to be enjoyable. Because the teacher employed a translation strategy when teaching vocabulary. The practice of conveying information from one language (the source language) into another is called translation technique (target language). The student receives the text from the teacher, at which point they add new terms and look up their definitions in dictionaries. However, when the teaching and learning process was carried out, they were actually bored and found it challenging to absorb the content.

With the clustering technique, it is the students who are in charge of the teaching and learning process; the teacher only serves as a guide. The teaching and learning processes include the students directly. The clustering technique leverages context cues to make vocabulary acquisition for pupils simpler. With this approach, all students participate actively and are motivated. It is useful for enhancing monologue speech habits and abilities.

According to Macdonald (1996:34), a free associated listing is a form of clustering approach. It starts with a central word that serves as a catalyst for the creation of related terms that branch out from the central term. One term leads to another and another, building a complicated web of disparate concepts that are all connected to the primary stimulus word in the same way.

The clustering technique is essentially a pre-writing strategy used to refine an idea before writing a paragraph. A type of free-associated listing is clustering. When new words are encountered, they can be put into the cluster's most appropriate position, which always presents a good opportunity to revise connected terms, according to Nation (1990:97). By encouraging learners to consider words with similar meanings and arrange them in the form of a bubble diagram, the clustering strategy aims to increase the relationship that students create with words and so improve access to the vocabulary.

Additionally, according to Sinaga (2007), students have the opportunity to demonstrate their ability to build a specific piece of knowledge that has been provided, connect it with other terms that are connected, and arrange it into a cluster. Through the use of the clustering technique, students are actively involved in connecting the context clues provided with the existing vocabulary they already know. They then have to create the entire words in a kind of bubble diagram that shows the connection between the new word and remaining words.

It is possible to gather many points of view in the cluster approach to education through the study and analysis of related research. The cluster strategy is as follows:

- To be a distinct field (e.g., economics, education), a technique for enhancing organizational forms of industrial integration that are aiming for competitive effectiveness

- A tool for developing support for innovations in the "Education-science Production" system that combines the needs of production and training. A group of interrelated economic entities that are incorporated into the organizational structure on the basis of a modern and regular approach.

- A creative and efficient method of developing the human capital necessary for the organization's future economic success - A reorganization of the educational system based on a

consistent guiding principle based on the outcomes of the integration of diverse educational institutions (kindergarten-school-college-university).

Seven essential cluster strategies are outlined by the researchers:

- Geographic strategy: sorts of clusters that range in size from tiny local to enormous worldwide;
- Lateral strategy: clusters that combine entities into different structures that can result in economies of scale and new combinations;
- Horizontal strategy: an extended cluster form made up of multiple clusters;
- Vertical strategy: combining one, which entails combining several clusters of subjects at the same level;
- Focused strategy-clusters centered on a single core;
- Technology strategy-clusters that are discernible in a collection of structures that employ the same technology;
- Quality strategy-clusters that are the center of how organizations implement collaboration.

It will be feasible to assess the current situation, precisely predict the results, take prompt action, and alter organizational management when appropriate educational techniques are formed in the management structure of educational institutions. The cluster education system offers the ideal strategy for resolving these problems. Since they incorporate all resources-material, financial, technological, informational, methodological, and human-cluster integration procedures are regarded as the most potent. To secure mutual confidence, the cluster enables you to flexibly construct a management system for your organizations and anticipate true development. A cluster environment can be created thanks to existing qualitative changes in educational system components, content activities, general and particular management functions, programs, technologies, and methodologies, as well as procedures for the participants' human resource development.

The cluster in education is a recent development. But due of its diversity, it already has a prominent position and has great potential (Tereshin & Volodin, 2010). There is no denying that the education sector in the modern world carries a significant amount of risk and uncertainty regarding some operational outcomes (Asadullin, 2009). Nevertheless, by overcoming these obstacles and fostering basic and applied scientific, economic, and social progress, new integrative structures will improve education quality and university competitiveness on the market for educational services (Karamursov, 2009). Positive modifications brought about by the educational cluster's activity include:

1. The creation of conditions for ensuring access to qualified primary, secondary and higher vocational education for young people;
2. the development and implementation of programs for continuous multilevel education that combine research institutions and institutions of secondary and higher vocational education, allowing for the possibility of adapting educational programs to the changing demands of the real economy and the conditions of the labor market; 1. the creation of conditions to ensure that young people have access to qualified primary, secondary, and higher vocational education; 2.
3. the accumulation, maintenance, and enhancement of ethical, cultural, and intellectual values;

4. Initiatives based on market needs formulation, taking into account the potential for both national and regional development, and the region's actual needs for highly qualified workers;

5. Cost reduction in the scientific-industrial orientation educational process. 6. Training of highly skilled specialists who are capable, accountable, fluent in their professions, orientated in related fields, and prepared for continuous professional progress, social mobility, and the labor market.

7. Establishment of a system for creating personnel reserves at the pre-university, university, and post-graduate training levels; specialists may be chosen based on their potential for learning and future employment in organizations

8. Developing cutting-edge science and integrating education, science, and production systems, including integrating scientific research into the educational process through the implementation of cutting-edge educational programs

9. The establishment of a maintenance system for specialists as they adjust to the industrial and social environment.

The clustering technique, also known as mapping, webbing, looping, or diagramming, is a useful way to condense a large subject into a focused and more manageable way of teaching, especially when teaching vocabulary. It is yet another efficient method for both teaching vocabulary and gathering data for an essay. Free association is used during clustering. Start with a blank sheet of paper to group ideas. Write and circle the word or phrase that best conveys the general topic you wish to write about in the center of the page. Clustering, according to another expert, is a method for developing an outline from the broadest concepts to the most particular ones at the beginning of a topic. (1985, Thomas E). Understanding the connections between specifics, arranging data in an organized manner, and creating granular evidence for the primary ideas are all advantageous.

Word maps can be used to show how words relate to one another. Create word maps by placing the main word in the center of the page and encouraging the kids to think of terms that are connected. As in a simple mind map, connect these words from the brainstorm to the target word. The word maps could consist of:

a. Words that have the same meaning as the focal word; b. Words that belong to the same word family.

c. Words with the same subject or theme;

d. The emphasis term can have multiple meanings; however, you should only do this if the students are confident in their understanding of the words most common usage. Otherwise, they might become perplexed.

Students that use word maps can relate new words to their existing knowledge. They demonstrate the connections between words' concepts. By illuminating these connections, pupils are better able to adapt their current conceptual frameworks (schema) and create deeper meaning when they encounter textual terms.

From the idea presented above, it is clear that clustering is a technique that may be utilized to produce content for a paper. For those who prefer to think visually, this strategy can be useful. Use lines, boxes, arrows, and circles to depict relationships between the ideas and information that are present when clustering. To create clustering, follow these steps:

1. Start by declaring your topic briefly in the middle of a blank page of paper. When new concepts and details occur, group them into boxes or circles and use connecting lines to demonstrate how they relate.

2. Recognize that there is no correct or incorrect way to cluster or draw data. It is a means to consider how numerous concepts and facts relate to one another on paper.

Clustering Technique encouraged students to memorize and retain their vocabulary easily and to enjoy the class activities. It also increased students' achievement and motivation and had a positive impact on their four English skills. These are some of the conclusions that can be drawn from the research.

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